

Codescape

Developed by: RWTH Aachen University

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Keywords

C, Computer Science, Java, Javascript, Mathematics, Programming, Python, Technology

Introduction

The serious game Codescape, developed in 2016 at the RWTH Aachen University, is used in several introductory programming courses and is designed explicitly for self-regulated learning from home. Codescape is a 2D browser game with map-based levels where you control a dog by writing the correct code to complete each stage. The game supports the simultaneous use of multiple programming languages and is modular, allowing it to fit the specific needs of various usage scenarios or lectures. Codescape was developed to level out students' initially heterogeneous skill levels and provide beginners with a playful, small-stepped introduction to imperative programming without requiring a local toolchain setup.

Facts

Release date:	14.10.2016
Developer:	RWTH Aachen University
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	10,000 per installation
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	A few minutes per level up to several hours per module, 32 levels in total
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Tablet, Laptop, or PC with Internet connection
Material:	–
Price:	At RWTH Aachen University, it is part of the CLS's service offering; licensing for external universities is available.

Resonance & Criticism

The game has been around since 2016 and has generated over 2 million submissions. Player feedback was collected via an in-game questionnaire. The game was well-received overall. 73% rated the game's difficulty as spot-on. The graphics were also mostly rated positively. Most players (66%) stated that the game helps to understand the lecture material better. Most gamers (75%) found the space setting to be good, and 42% said they would like to play the game in their free time.

Game principle & Process

Figure 1. Example gameplay from Codescape, showing the combination of level-based navigation and text-based programming (RWTH Aachen University). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

As a player, you explore a runaway spaceship. In the Codescape level, the students guide a robotic companion (RB) in the form of a dog from a starting point to a target point (see Figure 1). The Codescape spaceship is divided into seven decks, each with 32 levels and mini-games. The decks group the learning material by content and are unlocked as progress is made in the lecture to encourage continuous learning. As a challenge, they need to survive and stay within a command-line length limit that varies by level and programming language.

There are obstacles to overcome, such as randomly turning on and off lasers and holes in the floor. Each time a start button is pressed, the program is compiled on the server, executed, and the RB's path through the level is visualized as an animation. To increase replay value and offer more challenges for experienced students, additional game elements are introduced: power cells are added as a secondary target. These cells are placed at the levels in such a way that they can only be collected using advanced programming constructs.

Not every programming concept is suitable for mapping as a game level. In this case, we offer additional tasks in the form of puzzles, drag-and-drop, and multiple-choice. The storytelling components, including the intro video, avatars, and dialogues, complete the serious game.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Codescape aims to give beginners a playful, step-by-step introduction to imperative programming concepts, including loops, conditions, algorithms, Boolean logic, and recursion. There are levels for special algorithms and programming techniques.

The serious game was developed to accompany an introductory programming class and is suitable for schoolchildren and students. The players usually play unsupervised from home and on their own devices.

Effectiveness

There are no studies on the effectiveness of Codescape.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

There is no support for object-oriented content yet.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Johannes Christian Mieth

Sources

Gamper, Paul & Schroeder, Ulrik. (2023). Codescape - Development and Operation of a Serious Game for Teaching Programming in Introductory Courses. 335-341. 10.1007/978-3-031-44751-8_26.